

Photoelasticity of CNGS Crystals

B. Mytsyk^{a, *}, A. Erba^b, J. Maul^b, N. Demyanyshyn^a, P. Shchepanskyi^c,
and O. Syrotynsky^d

^a *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NAS of Ukraine, 5 Naukova Street, 79060 Lviv, Ukraine*

^b *Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Torino, Via Giuria 5, 10125 Torino, Italy*

^c *Ivan Franko Lviv National University, 19 Dragomanova St., Lviv 79005, Ukraine*

^d *Lviv Polytechnic National University, 12 Bandery St., 79046 Lviv, Ukraine*

*Corresponding author: mytsykb@ukr.net

All piezo-optic coefficients (POCs) and elasto-optic coefficients (ELOCs) of $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (CNGS) and $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (CTGS) trigonal crystals of the langasite group are determined from quantum-mechanical calculations based on hybrid density functional theory, as implemented in the CRYSTAL program. Calculation results for CTGS crystals are compared with experimental data. Indicative surfaces of piezo- and elasto-optic effects are constructed on the basis of the POCs and ELOCs matrices of CNGS crystals and the largest values of these effects are determined. The maximum values of the coefficient of acousto-optic figure of merit M_2 of the CNGS crystal are determined for the geometries of elasto-optic interaction which correspond to the maxima of the elasto-optic effect. These results are compared with the corresponding results for CTGS and langasite crystals. The spectral dependence of POCs and ELOCs of CNGS and CTGS crystals on the light wavelength is investigated in the 600...1500 nm range.

Keywords: piezo-optic coefficients; elasto-optic coefficients; indicative surfaces; acousto-optic efficiency; CNGS crystals.

1. Introduction

Crystals of $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (CNGS) and $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (CTGS) belong to the langasite $\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{SiO}_{14}$ (LGS) group which has more than 100 representatives (see, for instance, papers [1–3]). Note that the langasite-type crystals, for example, LGS, LGN ($\text{La}_3\text{Nb}_{0.5}\text{Ga}_{5.5}\text{O}_{14}$), and LGT ($\text{La}_3\text{Ta}_{0.5}\text{Ga}_{5.5}\text{O}_{14}$) have excellent characteristics, such as large piezoelectric coefficients (the d_{11} coefficient is three times greater than respective in crystalline quartz), large coefficients of electromechanical coupling, high temperature stability of these and other characteristics, absence of phase transitions up to melting temperatures ($\sim 1470^\circ\text{C}$) [3–6], ultra-low attenuation of acoustic waves (five times lower than in quartz crystal) [7]. Owing to this, these crystals find application in practice [3,4]. However, the LGS, LGN, and LGT crystals are expensive due to the high content of gallium (Ga) [8–10]. Therefore, other crystals of the LGS group were grown, in which the content of the Ga element is almost 2 times lower [8,9]. CNGS and CTGS belong to such crystals. In addition to the lower cost, these crystals exhibit a better thermal stability of their main characteristics. For example, according to [11,12], the smallest coefficients of temperature expansion (α_i) of quartz crystals and LGS are $7.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $3.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively, while CNGS have the value of $\alpha_i = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, both in the direction of the X_1 and X_3 axes [12]. In addition, the short-wavelength limit of the transmission spectrum of CNGS and CTGS crystals is

250 ... 275 nm [12–17], being approximately 100 nm lower than that of LGS [12,18]. This is important when using CNGS and CTGS crystals in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum. Other characteristics of these crystals have been thoroughly studied. For example, the piezoelectric coefficients $d_{11} = 3.7 \dots 4.63$ pC/N (according to various sources) and $d_{14} = -10 \dots -15.8$ pC/N and the electromechanical coupling coefficient $k_{12} = 0.10 \dots 0.12$ are comparable for both crystals and change slightly with temperature [5,10,16,19–24]. Particularly stable in terms of dielectric constant $\varepsilon_{11}(T)$ and thermal expansion coefficients α_1 and α_3 is the CNGS crystal [12, 25]. The elastic constants of these crystals differ slightly in magnitude, some of them by a factor of 2 [19,26,27]. The optical characteristics, on the contrary, such as transmission in the transparency region, refractive indices, and optical activity of both crystals are close [2,9,12–5,28,29]. As for the photoelastic characteristics (piezo-optic π_{im} and elasto-optic p_{ik} coefficients and acousto-optic efficiency), they have been investigated only for LGS and CTGS crystals [30,31]. It was concluded that CTGS crystals have the prospect of being used in acousto-optic devices for modulating light in the ultraviolet range [31].

In this work, the photoelastic characteristics of CNGS crystals are determined. This is accomplished by performing quantum-mechanical simulations within the hybrid density functional theory (DFT) approach, the effectiveness of which has been demonstrated in a number of works (see, for example, [32,33]). The π_{im} and p_{ik} coefficients of CTGS crystals are also determined using this method. Comparison of the obtained results with the experimental data for CTGS [31] additionally confirms the effectiveness of such quantum-mechanical approach for the determination of photoelastic characteristics and, accordingly, the reliability of the results obtained for CNGS crystals.

2. Calculation method and results

All quantum-mechanical calculations on CTGS and CNGS crystals have been performed with the CRYSTAL23 program [34], which implements fully-automated algorithms for the determination of elastic [35–37], piezoelectric [38], photoelastic [39], and piezo-optic [32] tensors of crystals of any symmetry. The hybrid PBE0 functional of the DFT is used [40], which is known to provide accurate strain-related properties of solids [41–44]. The POB-TZVP-rev2 atom-centered Gaussian-type function basis set has been adopted for all elements [45–47]. Reciprocal space is sampled according to a Monkhorst-Pack grid defined by a shrinking factor of 8, corresponding to 65 k-points in the symmetry-irreducible portion of the first Brillouin zone. Convergence of the self-consistent field step of the calculations is determined by a threshold on the energy set to 10^{-10} Hartree. The equilibrium structure of the system is determined by allowing for a full structural relaxation: the optimized lattice parameters are $a = 8.144$ and $c = 5.019$ Å for CTGS, and $a = 8.137$ and $c = 5.020$ Å for CNGS. CTGS and CNGS are two iso-structural crystals with very similar lattice parameters. Inspection of their computed electronic band structure confirms their similarity, with the most relevant difference being a lower band gap for CNGS than for CTGS of about 0.5 eV (6.78 eV for CTGS and 6.26 eV for CNGS).

The main experimental method for determining piezo-optic coefficients (POCs) π_{im} is the interferometric method [30,31,48–50]. To refine the values of some π_{im} POCs, the conoscopic method [51,52] is also used. These methods are extremely laborious. Crystals of CNGS and CTGS belong to 32 symmetry class (P321 space group). Accordingly, they have eight independent components of piezo-optic π_{im} and elasto-optic p_{ik} tensors [48,53]. It is especially difficult to experimentally determine non-main coefficients π_{14} , π_{41} , π_{44} , p_{14} , p_{41} , and p_{44} . All the piezo-optic

coefficients (POCs) π_{im} and elasto-optic coefficients (ELOCs) p_{ik} of CNGS and CTGS crystals are given in Table 1 and 2 as computed with the quantum-mechanical approach for the laser light wavelength ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm); here the indices i , m , and k denote, respectively, the direction of oscillation of the light wave vector (i.e. direction of light polarization), direction of uniaxial pressure, and direction of deformation. Experimental values of π_{im} and p_{ik} for CTGS crystals determined in [31] are also included in these tables; here, all the π_{im} coefficients were determined by the interferometric method, and p_{ik} were obtained based on the well-known tensor expression $p_{ik} = \pi_{im}C_{mk}$ (C_{mk} are the elastic stiffness coefficients).

3. Analysis of the results

3.1. Comparison of POCs and ELOCs for CNGS and CTGS crystals

From Tables 1 and 2 one can see that the majority of the calculated π_{im} and p_{ik} coefficients of CTGS crystals coincide with experimental data within the experimental error of determining these coefficients. Only for coefficients π_{11} , π_{12} and p_{12} there is a difference between calculated and experimental data. The anisotropy of POE and ELOE can be estimated by the inequalities $|\pi_{11}| < \pi_{12} > \pi_{13} < \pi_{31} < |\pi_{33}| > \pi_{14} > \pi_{41} < |\pi_{44}|$ (same for p_{ik} coefficients): it is the same for both crystals. The π_{31} and π_{33} POCs have the maximum values for both crystals. However, the maximum value of POE is significantly larger, as it is formed by several π_{im} coefficients (for more details on this and on the anisotropy of POE and ELOE of CNGS crystals see below in Section 3.3).

The calculated values of POCs and ELOCs for CNGS and CTGS are close for both crystals. There is a certain logic in this, since these crystals are close in terms of chemical formula, geometrical structure (they belong to the ordered structures of the LGS group [20]), and electronic structure.

Table 1. All independent piezo-optic coefficients π_{im} of CNGS and CTGS crystals (in units of Br, 1 Br = 1 Brewster = 10^{-12} m²/N).

π_{im}	π_{11}	π_{12}	π_{13}	π_{31}	π_{33}	π_{14}	π_{41}	π_{44}
CNGS (calculation)	-0.40	0.69	0.41	1.02	-1.13	0.81	0.41	-0.79
CTGS (calculation)	-0.48	0.88	0.40	1.03	-1.12	0.65	0.35	-0.84
CTGS (experiment [31])	-0.19 ± 0.06	0.22 ± 0.09	0.53 ± 0.12	1.40 ± 0.19	-1.20 ± 0.09	0.72 ± 0.11	0.32 ± 0.11	-0.81 ± 0.40

Table 2. All independent elasto-optic coefficients p_{ik} of CNGS and CTGS crystals.

p_{ik}	p_{11}	p_{12}	p_{13}	p_{31}	p_{33}	p_{14}	p_{41}	p_{44}
CNGS (calculation)	0.017	0.116	0.119	0.160	-0.107	0.036	0.037	-0.036
CTGS (calculation)	0.019	0.137	0.126	0.163	-0.104	0.031	0.031	-0.039
CTGS (experiment [31])	0.008 ± 0.010	0.044 ± 0.013	0.096 ± 0.022	0.165 ± 0.031	-0.088 ± 0.031	0.029 ± 0.005	0.029 ± 0.015	-0.033 ± 0.017

3.2. Dispersion of POCs and ELOCs

The dependence of π_{im} and p_{ik} coefficients on the light wavelength λ for CNGS and CTGS crystals is shown in Fig. 1 and 2. It follows from Fig. 1 that the POCs weakly depend on λ in the spectral range of 600 ... 1500 nm. However, it can be noted that the largest coefficient $\pi_{66} = \pi_{11} - \pi_{12}$ (this equality corresponds to the POC matrix in symmetry class 32 [11,48]) for the CTGS crystal increases almost monotonically with decrease of λ and has the largest $d\pi_{66}/d\lambda$ coefficient. The elasto-optic effect also shows a weak dependence on λ (Fig. 2). The largest coefficients p_{31} , p_{13} , and p_{12} slightly decrease as λ decreases, the coefficient $dp_{44}/d\lambda \rightarrow \text{const}$, and only p_{33} ELOC significantly increases for both crystals when λ approaches 600 nm. We emphasize that the study of the spectral dependence of POCs and ELOCs by experimental methods is too difficult a task, while it is accessible through the quantum-mechanical simulations performed for this study.

Fig. 1. Dependence of π_{im} piezo-optic coefficients on light wavelength for CNGS (left panel) and CTGS (right panel) crystals.

Fig. 2. Dependence of p_{ik} elasto-optic coefficients on light wavelength for CNGS (left panel) and CTGS (right panel) crystals.

3.3. Examples of anisotropy of photoelasticity in CNGS crystals

The anisotropy of piezo- and elasto-optic effects can be studied by various methods (see, for example, works [54–60]). Here we present several examples of analysis of POE and ELOE anisotropy in CNGS crystals based on the indicative surfaces (ISs). Mathematically, the IS expression corresponds to the law of transformation of components of higher-rank tensors when moving from one coordinate system to another. For example, for an IS of POE (tensor of the 4th rank), this expression is written as $\pi'_{ijkl} = \alpha_{im}\alpha_{jn}\alpha_{kp}\alpha_{lo}\pi_{mnpq}$ [53–56], where π'_{ijkl} is a specific component of the POC tensor in the new coordinate system, and π_{mnpq} are all the components of the POC tensor in the "old" (crystal-physical) coordinate system. In order to construct an IS based on the equation for π'_{ijkl} it is necessary to open the right-hand side of this equation, taking into account non-zero and independent POCs π_{mnpq} , and write down the corresponding direction cosines $\alpha_{im}, \alpha_{jn}, \alpha_{kp}, \alpha_{lo}$ of the radius vector \mathbf{R} , which describes the IS, in the spherical coordinate system θ, φ : $\alpha_{r1} = \sin\theta\cos\varphi, \alpha_{r2} = \sin\theta\sin\varphi, \alpha_{r3} = \cos\theta$ [54–56], where the r index indicates the direction of the radius vector \mathbf{R} , and indices 1, 2, 3 are the directions of the $X_1, X_2,$ and X_3 axes of the crystal-physical coordinate system.

Depending on how the geometric conditions of the photoelastic interaction are specified for the light wave vectors \mathbf{i} and the direction \mathbf{m} of the action of uniaxial pressure or the direction \mathbf{k} of the deformation (collinear, orthogonal or arbitrarily oriented directions), expressions for the ISs for longitudinal and transverse POE or arbitrarily selected POE or ELOE geometry can be obtained based on the expression for π'_{ijkl} (see, for example, [52–57]).

If the direction of the uniaxial pressure vector \mathbf{m} is related to the spherical coordinates θ_m, φ_m , and the direction of the polarization vector of the light wave \mathbf{i} is related to the spherical

coordinates θ_i , φ_i , then, based on the expression for π'_{ijkl} and by taking into account the non-zero components of the POC matrix of crystals belonging to the 32 symmetry class [48], one can obtain the well-known expression [56] for the IS, the radius vector of which $\mathbf{R} = \pi'_{im}$ describes the POE at arbitrary directions \mathbf{i} of light polarization and at the actions of uniaxial pressure in any given direction \mathbf{m} :

$$\begin{aligned} \pi'_{im} = & [\pi_{11} \sin^2 \theta_m \cos^2(\varphi_m - \varphi_i) + \pi_{12} \sin^2 \theta_m \sin^2(\varphi_m - \varphi_i) + \pi_{13} \cos^2 \theta_m + \\ & + 0.5 \pi_{14} \sin 2\theta_m \sin(\varphi_m + 2\varphi_i)] \sin^2 \theta_i + (\pi_{31} \sin^2 \theta_m + \pi_{33} \cos^2 \theta_m) \cos^2 \theta_i + \\ & + [\pi_{41} \sin^2 \theta_m \sin(2\varphi_m + \varphi_i) + 0.5 \pi_{44} \sin 2\theta_m \cos(\varphi_m - \varphi_i)] \sin 2\theta_i. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here and below we use the matrix form of the POCs [48,53]: $\pi_{im} = \pi_{ijkl}$ if $m = 1, 2, 3$; and $\pi_{im} = 2\pi_{ijkl}$ if $m = 4, 5, 6$.

For practical application, important are the orthogonal conditions for the directions of light propagation and uniaxial pressure action. Then, for crystals of 32 symmetry class, when the vectors of light polarization \mathbf{i} and the action of uniaxial pressure \mathbf{m} coincide and, accordingly, $\theta = \theta_m = \theta_i$, and $\varphi = \varphi_m = \varphi_i$, the expression for the IS of the longitudinal POE ($\mathbf{i} \parallel \mathbf{m}$) has the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi'_{ii}(\theta, \varphi) = & \pi_{11} \sin^4 \theta + \pi_{33} \cos^4 \theta + (\pi_{13} + \pi_{31} + 2\pi_{44}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \\ & + (\pi_{14} + 2\pi_{41}) \sin^3 \theta \cos \theta \sin 3\varphi. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

There are two options for constructing ISs for transverse POE ($\mathbf{i} \perp \mathbf{m}$). The first option is when the spherical coordinates, specifying the directions of the \mathbf{i} and \mathbf{m} vectors, are connected by ratios $\theta_m = 90^\circ$, $\varphi_m = \varphi_i + 90^\circ$. By applying these conditions to (1), one can obtain the IS for the polarization:

$$\pi'_{im}^{(i)} = \pi_{12} \sin^2 \theta_i + \pi_{31} \cos^2 \theta_i - 2\pi_{41} \sin \theta_i \cos \theta_i \sin 3\varphi_i, \quad (3)$$

where index (i) indicates that the IS is described by a radius vector that coincides with the direction of polarization of the light wave \mathbf{i} .

The second option of constructing ISs corresponds to the condition $\theta_i = 90^\circ$, $\varphi_i = \varphi_m + 90^\circ$. Then the piezo-optic surface is described by a radius vector coinciding with the direction \mathbf{m} of uniaxial pressure actions. Such a surface is called the IS of a mechanical stress and is denoted as $\pi'_{im}^{(m)}$:

$$\pi'_{im}^{(m)} = \pi_{12} \sin^2 \theta_m + \pi_{13} \cos^2 \theta_m - \pi_{14} \sin \theta_m \cos \theta_m \sin 3\varphi_m. \quad (4)$$

The same relations can be written for the analysis of the anisotropy of the elasto-optic effect, when the deformation direction \mathbf{k} corresponds to spherical coordinates θ_k and φ_k (this was done, for example, for the CaWO_4 crystal in work [55]).

The examples of ISs and their sections in the X_2X_3 plane for POE of CNGS crystal are presented in Fig. 3 (a) and (b). These are constructed on the basis of expressions (2) and (3) and the π_{im} values of POCs taken from Table 1. The surfaces for CNGS crystals are visually similar to the POE surfaces of CTGS crystal [54]. As can be seen from Fig. 3 (a), the surface of the longitudinal POE is significantly anisotropic, with a change in the sign of the extrema and zero values of the effect in the corresponding directions. The maximum value of the longitudinal POE

in CNGS, like in CTGS [54], lies on the X_3 axis of the indicative surface and corresponds to POC $\pi_{33} = -1.13$ Br.

The highest values of POE and ELOE in the CNGS crystal, like in CTGS crystal [54], are observed for the transverse effect (see Fig. 3 (b), (c)). The maximum values of transverse POE and ELOE and the directions corresponding to these values are determined on the basis of expression (3) and a similar expression for ELOE by the method of partial derivatives.

Fig. 3. Examples of ISs of POE and ELOE of CNGS crystal and their cross-sections in the X_2X_3 plane: (a) longitudinal POE π'_{ii} (in units of Br); (b) transverse POE $\pi'_{im}^{(i)}$ (in units of Br); (c) transverse ELOE $p'_{in}^{(i)}$.

Let us define, for example, the value of the maximum transverse POE for the case presented in Fig. 3 (b) and the spherical coordinates of the direction in which it is observed. Based on the expression for the surface (3), one can obtain the expression for its intersection with the plane X_2X_3 . For this, it is necessary to substitute in (3) the condition $\varphi_i = 90^\circ$, which is corresponding to such an intersection. The result is

$$\pi'_{im}^{(i)} = \pi_{12} \sin^2 \theta_i + \pi_{31} \cos^2 \theta_i + 2\pi_{41} \sin \theta_i \cos \theta_i. \quad (5)$$

From the analysis of the partial derivative $\frac{\partial \pi'_{im}^{(i)}}{\partial \theta_i} = 0$, which describes the maximum POE at the intersection (5), one can obtain the expression for determining the angle θ_i :

$$\theta_i = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{arctg} \frac{-2\pi_{41}}{\pi_{12} - \pi_{31}}. \quad (6)$$

The θ_i angle for CNGS crystal is 34° (Fig. 3 (b)). The indicated value of the angle θ_i and the maximum value of POE are observed for the intersection, which is given by the already mentioned condition of $\varphi_i = 90^\circ$. By substituting the angle $\theta_i = 34^\circ$ in expression (5), one can obtain the maximum value of the IS of the transverse POE of the CNGS crystal $\pi_{im}^{(i)} = 1.30$ Br. Let us emphasize that this value of POE is significantly greater than the large positive POC $\pi_{31} = 1.02$ Br, since, according to expression (5), it is formed by three positive POCs π_{12} , π_{31} and π_{41} . Similarly, the maximum value of the IS of the transverse ELOE can be found, giving $p_{ik}^{\prime(i)} = 0.179$ and the corresponding values of the angles $\theta_i = 29^\circ$ and $\varphi_i = 90^\circ$ (Fig. 3 (c)).

The surfaces of the longitudinal POE for CNGS crystal do not require special analysis, since, as can be seen from Fig. 3 (a), the maximum value of POE in this crystal lie on the X_3 axis, that is, it corresponds to the condition of $\theta_i = \theta_m = 0^\circ$. By substituting this condition into equation (1), one can make sure that the maxima of longitudinal POE correspond to the coefficient π_{33} .

It can be concluded on the basis of the conducted analysis that the photoelastic properties of CTGS and CNGS crystals are comparable in magnitude, but differ in anisotropy. For example, the maxima of POE and ELOE lie in the main plane X_2X_3 ($\varphi_i = 90^\circ$) and for CTGS correspond to angle [54] $\theta_i = 14^\circ$ for POE ($\pi_{im}^{(i)} = 1.48$ Br), $\theta_i = 13^\circ$ for ELOE ($p_{ik}^{\prime(i)} = 0.172$), and for CNGS these angles are 34° and 29° for POE and ELOE, respectively (see Fig. 3 (b), (c)).

3.4. Assessment of acousto-optic (AO) efficiency

The value of AO efficiency is estimated on the basis of the known expression for the acousto-optic figure of merit $M_2 = n_i^6 p_{ik}^2 / (\rho V_k^3)$, where n_i is the refractive index of the crystal, ρ its density, V_k the velocity of acoustic wave; the i index denotes the direction of light polarization, and index k the direction of deformation and propagation of the acoustic wave in the crystal.

The values of the M_2 coefficient for the largest p_{ik} ELOCs of CTGS and LGS crystals, defined in [31], are $1.66 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$ and $0.89 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$, respectively. Here, let us define the M_2 for the largest p_{31} ELOC of the CNGS crystal. First, let's obtain the refractive index of this crystal for the laser light wavelength $\lambda = 632.8$ nm. For this, the Zelmeyer formula and the Zelmeyer coefficients for CNGS specified in [13] were used, and the following values were obtained: $n_1 = n_2 = n_o = 1.7879$, $n_3 = n_e = 1.8778$. Let's substitute in the formula for M_2 the value of ELOC $p_{31} = 0.16$ (Table 1), the refractive index n_3 and the value $V_1 = 6.15 \cdot 10^3$ m/s [27], which correspond to the coefficient p_{31} , as well as the crystal density $\rho = 4.12 \cdot 10^3$ kg/m³ [8]. The result is: $M_2 = 1.17 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$. Therefore, by the M_2 value, the CNGS crystal is superior to langasite and inferior to the CTGS crystal.

Let us calculate M_2 for the largest value $p_{ik}^{\prime(i)} = 0.179$ of ELOE, see Fig. 3 (c). To do this, one should find the value of the refractive index n'_i along the direction given by the angle $\theta_i = 29^\circ$, Fig. 3 (c). This value of n'_i can be found from the expression $n'_i = (\sin^2 \theta_i / n_1^2 + \cos^2 \theta_i / n_3^2)^{-1/2}$, which is easily obtained based on the equation for the optical indicatrix and the equation of the straight line $x_2 = x_3 \tan \theta_i$, $x_1 = 0$ intersecting the indicatrix in the X_2X_3 plane. For the angle of $\theta_i =$

29°, the value of $n'_i = 1.8555$ is obtained. By substituting the above values of $p'^{(i)}_{ik}$, n'_i , ρ , and V_1 into the expression for M_2 , one can obtain the value of $M_2 = 1.36 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$. The maximum M_2 values for LGS and CTGS crystals determined in [54] are $0.89 \cdot 10^{-12}$ and $1.79 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$, respectively. Therefore, the CNGS and CTGS crystals are significantly superior to LGS in terms of AO efficiency and are suitable for AO modulation of light in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum, especially considering that the lower limit of the transparency region of these crystals is 250 ... 275 nm, which is approximately 100 nm lower, than in LGS.

Thus, in this work, similarly as in works [32, 33], the effectiveness of the quantum mechanical calculation of the photoelastic characteristics of crystals is demonstrated. Therefore, when searching for effective photoelastic materials, it is sufficient to first evaluate their main characteristics (π_{im} , p_{ik} , M_2) on the basis of a quantum-mechanical calculations, and only in the case of obtaining special results should they be confirmed by experimental methods.

4. Conclusions

All components of the tensors of the piezo-optic π_{im} and elasto-optic p_{ik} effects of trigonal (32 symmetry class) $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ crystals (CNGS) were determined by the method of quantum-mechanical calculations, based on hybrid density functional theory. The results for CNGS are compared with the results for $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (CTGS) crystal. Examples of construction of indicative surfaces (ISs) of piezo- and elasto-optic effects (POE and ELOE) are provided. Based on the analysis of the equations of these surfaces using the method of partial derivatives, the geometries of POE and ELOE with the largest values were found. The acousto-optic figure of merit M_2 is determined for the largest elasto-optic coefficient and the largest ELOE value. It is concluded that CNGS and CTGS crystals are suitable for acousto-optic modulation of ultraviolet radiation, since the lower limit of the spectral range of transmission for these crystals is 250 ... 275 nm. The spectral dependence of all the π_{im} and p_{ik} coefficients in the range of 600 ... 1500 nm was also established from quantum-mechanical calculations; we stress that obtaining such dependence by experimental methods would be challenging. It is concluded that such quantum-mechanical calculations are quite suitable for express analysis of the photoelastic characteristics of crystalline materials, and only in the case of obtaining special results should they be confirmed by experimental methods.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Ukraine (Project 2020.02/0211) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 778156.

References

- [1] V.I. Chani, K. Shimamura, Y.M. Yu, and T. Fukuda, Design of new oxide crystals with improved structural stability, *Mat. Sci. Engineering R20* (1997) 281–338
- [2] A.F. Konstantinova, T.G. Golovina, B.V. Nabatov, A.P. Dudka, and B.V. Mill, Experimental and theoretical determination of the optical rotation in langasite family crystals, *Crystallogr. Rep.* 60 (2015) 907–914 <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063774515060140>

- [3] H. Ohsato, T. Iwataki, and H. Morikoshi, Mechanism of piezoelectricity for langasite based on the framework crystal structure, *Trans. Electr. Electron. Mater.* 13 (2) (2012) 51–59 <https://doi.org/10.4313/TEEM.2012.13.2.51>
- [4] H. Fritze, High-temperature bulk acoustic wave sensors, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 22 (2011) 012002 <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-0233/22/1/012002>
- [5] Sh. Zhang, H. Kong, R. Xia, Ya. Zheng, J. Xin, and T.R. Shrout, Growth and high-temperature electromechanical properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbX}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ ($X = \text{Ga}$ and Al) piezoelectric crystals, *Sol. State Comm.* 150 (2010) 435–438 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssc.2009.12.009>
- [6] G.K. Rane, M. Seifert, S. Menzel, T. Gemming, and J. Eckert, Tungsten as a chemically-stable electrode material on Ga-containing piezoelectric substrates langasite and catangasite for high-temperature SAW devices, *Materials* 9 (2016) 101 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma9020101>
- [7] A.A. Kaminskii, E.L. Belokoneva, B.V. Mill, Yu.V. Pisarevskii, S.E. Sarkisov, I.M. Silvestrova, A.V. Butashin, and G.G. Khodzhabagyan, Pure and Nd^{3+} -doped $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ga}_2\text{Ge}_4\text{O}_{14}$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{Ga}_2\text{Ge}_4\text{O}_{14}$ single crystals, their structure, optical, spectral luminescence, electromechanical properties, and stimulated emission, *Phys. Stat. Sol. (a)* 86 (1984) 345–362 <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.2210860139>
- [8] W.Q. Huang, and H. Yang, SAW properties on X,Y,Z-cut of $\text{Sr}_3(\text{Nb,Ta})\text{Ga}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ and $\text{Ca}_3(\text{Nb,Ta})\text{Ga}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ piezoelectric crystal, *Key Eng. Mat.* 512-515 (2012) 1207–1211 <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/KEM.512-515.1207>
- [9] A.Wu, J. Xu, J. Zhou, B. Lu, X. Wu, X. Li, and G. Qian, Bridgman growth of a novel piezoelectric single-crystal material: $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$, *Key Eng. Mat.* 336-338 (2007) 217–219 <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/KEM.336-338.217>
- [10] Y.Q. Zheng, S.-X. Cui, J.J. Chen, X.N. Tu, J. Xin, H.K. Kong, and E.W. Shi, Advances in design, growth and application of piezoelectric crystals with langasite structure, 2012 Symposium on Piezoelectricity, Acoustic Waves, and Device Applications (SPAWDA), 23-25 November 2012, Shanghai, China, *IEEE Xplore* (2013) 252–259 <https://doi.org/10.1109/SPAWDA.2012.6464083>
- [11] M.P. Shaskolskaya (editor), *Acoustic crystals. Handbook*, Nauka, 1982.
- [12] Z. Wang, X. Cheng, D. Yuan, L. Pan, S. Guo, D. Xu, and M. Lv, Crystal growth and properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystals, *J. Cryst. Growth* 249 (2003) 240–244 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0248\(02\)02112-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0248(02)02112-7)
- [13] X. Zhang, X. Zhang, S. Guo, J. He, K. Han, F. Lou, B. Zhang, R. Wang, and X. Liu, Growth and optical properties of a new CGG-type laser crystal Nd^{3+} : CNGS, *Opt. Mat. Express* 5 (2015) 977–985 <https://doi.org/10.1364/OME.5.000977>
- [14] O.A. Buzanov, N.S. Kozlova, A.P. Kozlova, E.V. Zabelina, A.E. Blagov, I.A. Eliovich, A.G. Kulikov, and A.V. Targonskiy, Crystal growth and optical properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystals, *Jap. J. Appl. Phys.* 57 (2018) 11UD08 <https://doi.org/10.7567/JJAP.57.11UD08>
- [15] X. Shi, D. Yuan, A. Wei, Z. Wang, and B. Wang, Growth and optical activity of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (CTGS) single crystal, *Mat. Res. Bull.* 41 (2006) 1052–1055 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2005.11.019>
- [16] X. Fu, E.G. Villora, Y. Matsushita, Y. Kitanaka, Y. Noguchi, M. Miyayama, K. Shimamura, and N. Ohashi, Influence of growth conditions on the optical, electrical resistivity and piezo-

- electric properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystals, *J. Ceramic Soc. Jap.* 124 523–527 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.2109/jcersj2.15293>
- [17] Sh. Kurosawa, M. Kitahara, Y. Yokota, K. Hishinuma, T. Kudo, O. Buzanov, A. Medvedev, V.I. Chani, and A. Yoshikawa, Scintillation properties of a non-doped $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ crystal, *IEEE Transact. Nuclear Sci.* 61 (2014) 339–342
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TNS.2013.2287123>
- [18] Z. Wang, D. Yuan, X. Cheng, D. Xu, M. Lv, L. Pan, X. Duan, H. Sun, X. Shi, Y. Lv, X. Wei, Z. Sun, C. Luan, S. Guo, G. Zhang, and X. Wang, The growth and properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystals, *J. Cryst. Growth.* 253 (2003) 378–382
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0248\(03\)01100-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0248(03)01100-X)
- [19] J. Ren, X. Zhang, X. Zhang, R. Cheng, J. Guo, X. Zhang, F. Yu, B. Huang, and S. Guo, Crystal growth, experimental and theoretical studies on the electronic structure of CNGS and Nd: CNGS, *Cryst. Eng. Comm.* 18 (2016) 3481–3487
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C6CE00361C>
- [20] D. Roshchupkin, L. Ortega, O. Plotitsyna, A. Erko, I. Zizak, S. Vadilong, D. Irzhak, E. Emelin, O. Buzanov, and W. Leitenberger, Piezoelectric $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ crystal: crystal growth, piezoelectric and acoustic properties, *Appl. Phys. A* (2016) 753
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-016-0279-1>
- [21] Sh. Zhang, Y. Zheng, H. Kong, J. Xin, E. Frantz, and T.R. Shrout, Characterization of high temperature piezoelectric crystals with an ordered langasite structure, *J. Appl. Phys.* 105 (2009) 114107 <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3142429>
- [22] H. Ohsato, T. Iwataki, and H. Morikoshi, Mechanism of piezoelectricity for langasite based on the framework crystal structure, *Trans. Electr. Electron. Mater.* 13 (2012) 51–59
<https://doi.org/10.4313/TEEM.2012.13.2.51>
- [23] H. Zu, H. Wu, Y. Wang, Sh. Zhang, T.R. Shrout, and Q. M. Wang, Properties of single crystal piezoelectric $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ and $\text{YCa}_4\text{O}(\text{BO}_3)$ resonators at high-temperature and vacuum conditions,” *Sensors and Actuators: A Physical.* 216 (2014) 167–175
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2014.05.017>
- [24] I.H. Jung, A. Yoshikawa, T. Fukuda, and K.H. Auh, Growth and structure of $\text{A}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ (A=Sr, Ca) compounds, *J. Alloys Comp.* 339 (2002) 149–155
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388\(01\)01961-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388(01)01961-2)
- [25] J. Ren, X. Zhang, X. Zhang, J. Guo, R.Cheng, and S. Guo, Growth and enhanced electro-elastic properties of Nd^{3+} : CNGS crystals with ordered langasite structure, *Mat. Lett.* 167 (2016) 122–124 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2015.12.168>
- [26] X. Shi, D. Yuan, X. Yin, A. Wei, Sh. Guo, and F. Yu, Crystal growth and dielectric, piezoelectric and elastic properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystal, *Sol. State Comm.* 142 (2007) 173–176 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssc.2007.01.047>
- [27] T. Karaki, R. Sato, M. Adachi, J.-I. Kushibiki, and M. Arakawa, Piezoelectric properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{NbGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystal, *Jap. J. Appl. Phys.* 43 (2004) 6721–6724
<https://doi.org/10.1143/JJAP.43.6721>
- [28] B. Wang, A. Wei, X. Shi, D. Yuan, and H. Qi, Optical properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ single crystal, *Mat. Lett.* 60 (2006) 2617–2619 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2006.01.110>

- [29] F. Chen, F. Yu, Sh. Hou, Y. Liu, Y. Zhou, X. Shi, H. Wang, Zh. Wang, and X. Zhao, Crystal growth and characterization of CTGS and Nd:CTGS for self-frequency-doubling applications, *Cryst. Eng. Comm.* 16 (2014) 10286–10291
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C4CE01740D>
- [30] B.G. Mytsyk, A.S. Andrushchak, and G.I. Gaskevich, Comprehensive studies of piezo-optical effect in langasite crystals, *Ukr. J. Phys.* 52 (2007) 798–808
- [31] B. Mytsyk, Y. Suhak, N. Demyanyshyn, O. Buryy, N. Syvorotka, D. Sugak, S. Ubizskii, and H. Fritze, Full set of piezo-optic and elasto-optic coefficients of $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$ crystals at room temperature, *Appl. Opt.* 59 (2020) 8951–8958 <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.398428>
- [32] A. Erba, M.T. Ruggiero, T.M. Korter, and R. Dovesi, Piezo-optic tensor of crystals from quantum-mechanical calculations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 143 (2015) 144504
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4932973>
- [33] B. Mytsyk, A. Erba, N. Demyanyshyn, and O. Sakharuk, Piezo-optic and elasto-optic effects in lead molybdate crystals, *Opt. Mater.* 62 (2016) 632–638
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2016.11.001>
- [34] A. Erba, J.K. Desmarais, S. Casassa, B. Civalleri, L. Donà, I. J. Bush, B. Searle, L. Maschio, L. Edith-Daga, A. Cossard, C. Ribaldone, E. Ascrizzi, N.L. Marana, J.-P. Flament and B. Kirtman, CRYSTAL23: A Program for computational solid state physics and chemistry, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c00958>
- [35] W. F. Perger, J. Criswell, B. Civalleri, and R. Dovesi, Ab-initio calculation of elastic constants of crystalline systems with the CRYSTAL code, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 180 (2009) 1753 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2009.04.022>
- [36] A. Erba, A. Mahmoud, R. Orlando, and R. Dovesi, Elastic properties of six silicate garnet end-members from accurate ab initio simulations, *Phys. Chem. Minerals* 41 (2014) 151–160
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-013-0630-4>
- [37] A. Erba, D. Caglioti, C.M. Zicovich-Wilson and R. Dovesi, Nuclear-relaxed elastic and piezoelectric constants of materials: Computational aspects of two quantum-mechanical approaches, *J. Comput. Chem.* 38 (2017) 257–264 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.24687>
- [38] A. Erba, Kh. E. El-Kelany, M. Ferrero, I. Baraille and M. Rérat, Piezoelectricity of SrTiO_3 : An ab initio description, *Phys. Rev. B* 88 (2013) 035102
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.88.035102>
- [39] A. Erba, and R. Dovesi, Photoelasticity of crystals from theoretical simulations, *Phys. Rev. B* 88 (2013) 045121 <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.88.045121>
- [40] C. Adamo, and V. Barone, Toward reliable density functional methods without adjustable parameters: The PBE0 model, *J. Chem. Phys.* 110 (1999) 6158–6170
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.478522>
- [41] A. Mahmoud, A. Erba, Kh. E. El-Kelany, M. Rérat, and R. Orlando, Low-temperature phase of BaTiO_3 : Piezoelectric, dielectric, elastic and photoelastic properties from ab initio simulations, *Phys. Rev. B* 89 (2014) 045103 <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.89.045103>
- [42] Kh. E. El-Kelany, A. Erba, Ph. Carbonnière, and M. Rérat, Piezoelectric, elastic, structural and dielectric properties of the $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x\text{O}_2$ solid solution: A theoretical study, *J. Phys.:*

- Condens. Matter. 26 (2014) 205401 <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/26/20/205401>
- [43] Kh.E. El-Kelany, Ph. Carbonnière, A. Erba, and M. Rérat, Inducing a finite in-plane piezoelectricity in graphene with low concentration of inversion symmetry-breaking defects, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 119 (2015) 8966–8973 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b01471>
- [44] Kh. E. El-Kelany, Ph. Carbonnière, A. Erba, J.-M. Sotiropoulos, and M. Rérat, Piezoelectricity of functionalized graphene: A quantum mechanical rationalization, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 120 (2016) 7795–7803 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b11929>
- [45] D. Vilela Oliveira, J. Laun, M.F. Peintinger, and T. Bredow, BSSE-correction scheme for consistent gaussian basis sets of double-and triple-zeta valence with polarization quality for solid-state calculations, *J. Comput. Chem.* 40 (2019) 2364–2376 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.26013>
- [46] J. Laun, and T. Bredow, BSSE-corrected consistent gaussian basis sets of triple-zeta valence with polarization quality of the sixth period for solid-state calculations, *J. Comput. Chem.* 42 (2021) 1064–1072 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.26521>
- [47] J. Laun, and T. Bredow, BSSE-corrected consistent gaussian basis sets of triple-zeta valence with polarization quality of the fifth period for solid-state calculations, *J. Comput. Chem.* 43 (2022) 839–846 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.26839>
- [48] T. S. Narasimhamurty, Photoelastic and electrooptic properties of crystals, New York: Springer (1981)
- [49] O. Krupych, M. Kushnirevych, O. Mys, and R. Vlokh, Photoelastic properties of NaBi(MoO₄)₂ crystals, *Appl. Opt.* 54 (2015) 5016–5023 <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.54.005016>
- [50] B. Mytsyk, T. Kryvyy, N. Demyanyshyn, O. Mys, I. Martynuyk-Lototska, O. Kokhan, and R. Vlokh, Piezo-, elasto- and acousto-optic properties of Tl₃AsS₄ crystals, *Appl. Opt.* 57 (2018) 3796–3801 <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.57.003796>
- [51] B.G. Mytsyk, Ya.P. Kost', N.M. Demyanyshyn, V.M. Gaba, and O.M. Sakharuk, Study of piezo-optic effect of calcium tungstate crystals by the conoscopic method, *Opt. Mater.* 39 (2015) 69–73 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2014.10.066>
- [52] B.G. Mytsyk, A.S. Andrushchak, D.M. Vynnyk, N.M. Demyanyshyn, Ya.P. Kost, and A.V. Kityk, Characterization of photoelastic materials by combined Mach-Zehnder and conoscopic interferometry: Application to tetragonal lithium tetraborate crystals, *Opt. Las. Eng.* 127 (2020) 105991 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2019.105991>
- [53] J. Nye, Physical properties of crystals, Oxford: Clarendon press (1964)
- [54] N.M. Demyanyshyn, Yu. Suhak, B.G. Mytsyk, O.A. Buryy, Yu.Ya. Maksishko, D. Sugak, and H. Fritze, Anisotropy of piezo-optic and elasto-optic effects in langasite family crystals, *Opt. Mat.* 119 (2021) 111284 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2021.111284>
- [55] N. Demyanyshyn, B. Mytsyk, Y. Kost, I. Solskii, and O. Sakharuk, Elasto-optic effect anisotropy in calcium tungstate crystals, *Appl. Opt.* 54 (2015) 2347–2355 <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.54.002347>
- [56] B. Mytsyk, and N. Demyanyshyn, Piezooptic surfaces of lithium niobate crystals, *Crystallogr. Rep.* 51 (2006) 653–660 <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063774506040195>

- [57] B. Mytsyk, Methods for the studies of piezooptic effect in crystals and analysis of the experimental data. II. Analysis of the experimental data, *Ukr. J. Phys. Opt.* 4 (2003) 105–118 <https://doi.org/10.3116/16091833/4/3/105/2003>
- [58] O. Buryy, N. Demyanyshyn, B. Mytsyk, and A. Andrushchak, Optimizing of the piezo-optic interaction geometry in SrB_4O_7 crystals, *Opt. Appl.* 46 (2016) 447–459 <https://doi.org/10.5277/oa160311>
- [59] N.M. Demyanyshyn, B.G. Mytsyk, A.S. Andrushchak, and O.V. Yurkevych, Anisotropy of the electro-optic effect in magnesium-doped LiNbO_3 crystals, *Crystallogr. Rep.* 54 (2009) 306–312 <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063774509020217>
- [60] O. Mys, M. Kostyrko, and R. Vlokh, Anisotropy of acousto-optic figure of merit for LiNbO_3 crystals: anisotropic diffraction, *Appl. Opt.* 55 (2016) 2439–2450 <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.55.002439>